

TABLE 1—STEPWISE METAL LIGAND STABILITY CONSTANTS AT 35°C AND IONIC STRENGTH 0.1M KNO₃

Metal ions	3-(<i>o</i> -hydroxyphenyl)-5-phenyl isoxazole			3-(<i>o</i> -hydroxyphenyl)-5- <i>p</i> -methoxyphenyl isoxazole			3-(<i>o</i> -hydroxyphenyl)-5- <i>p</i> -chlorophenyl isoxazole		
	log K ₁	log K ₂	log β	log K ₁	log K ₂	log β	log K ₁	log K ₂	log β
[H ⁺]	10.25	—	—	10.30	—	—	9.80	—	—
Ce ³⁺	—	—	—	6.8062	6.0511	12.8578	5.8092	5.2542	11.0634
Pr ³⁺	7.3771	6.8185	14.1956	7.2888	7.1584	14.4472	5.9411	5.4989	11.4400
Nd ³⁺	7.4424	6.9097	14.3521	7.3948	7.1496	14.5441	5.9542	5.6893	11.6435
Sm ³⁺	7.5250	7.3197	14.8447	7.5185	7.1805	14.6990	6.4064	6.0607	12.4771
Gd ³⁺	7.8142	7.3208	15.1350	7.3979	7.1245	14.5224	6.4064	6.0607	12.4771
Dy ³⁺	8.0645	7.7806	15.8451	7.6081	7.3175	14.9206	7.1139	6.7312	13.8400

It is evident from Table 1, that the order of stability of the metal chelates of all the ligands used with different rare earth metal ions were Dy³⁺ > Gd³⁺ > Sm³⁺ > Nd³⁺ > Pr³⁺ > Ce³⁺. The stability of the metal chelates increases with decrease in ionic radii. This may be due to varying degree of stabilisation arising out of interaction of 4f metal orbitals with the ligand field.

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A Method of Preparation of Copper Hydroxylapatite and its Solid Solutions with Arsenate

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COPPER hydroxylapatite (CuHA), Cu₁₀(PO₄)₆(OH)₂ is one of the very important compounds among the apatite series. It undergoes a series of cationic and anionic exchange reactions¹. Phosphate-arsenate exchange results in the formation of a series of solid solutions of copper

hydroxylapatite with arsenate according to the following equation :

Earlier methods of preparation solid solutions of CuHA with arsenate by the solid state reaction² were however found to be discontinuous and non-homogeneous. The present work is an attempt to prepare samples of these homogeneous solid solutions over the entire compositional range by the method of co-precipitation in aqueous media. Similar studies on Ca²⁺→Cu²⁺ exchange in hydroxylapatite were reported earlier³.

Experimental

Chemicals used for preparation of samples were either AR (BDH) or E. Merck (extra pure) grade. Samples were prepared by precipitation in CO₂-free atmosphere at 37 ± 0.5° by simultaneous dropwise addition of stoichiometric quantities of copper nitrate solution and a solution containing PO₄³⁻ and AsO₄³⁻ ions in the proportion desired for solid solution. All solutions were prepared separately in carbon dioxide free doubly distilled water and pH of these solutions were maintained above 11 by the addition of excess of liquor ammonia. Then a part of copper nitrate solution was taken in a 2L flask with a side tube fitted with a three-hole rubber stopper carrying two separating funnels through two holes and a delivery tube through the third hole. Both the solutions were taken separately in the separating funnels and were allowed to drop simultaneously into the flask. CO₂-free air was continuously bubbled which kept medium of precipitation well stirred. Precipitate alongwith mother liquor was aged by boiling under reflux for 30 min. to improve homogeneity and crystallinity of precipitate. Maintenance of desired pH during preparation was ensured by testing the filtrate after separation of the precipitate since any alteration of pH of the medium during precipitation leads to the formation of copper deficient apatites.

Samples dried at 100° for few hours were analysed complexometrically⁴ and their molar volumes were determined⁵.

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TABLE 1—CHEMICAL ANALYSES OF COPPER HYDROXYLAPATITE AND ITS SOLID SOLUTIONS WITH ARSENATE

Sample No.	Wt%			Molecular Formulae	Mol. wt.	Density	Molecular volume ml/mole	g. atom ratio Cu P+As	Lattice parameter	
	Cu	P	As						a	c
1.	51.27	15.01	—	$\text{Cu}_{10}(\text{FO}_4)_6(\text{OH})_2$	1289.5	3.565	347.68	1.664	8.83	6.53
2.	49.43	12.08	5.84	$\text{Cu}_{10}(\text{FO}_4)_5.0(\text{AsO}_4)_{1.0}(\text{OH})_2$	1283.42	3.580	358.50	1.662	8.98	6.65
3.	48.52	10.41	9.15	$\text{Cu}_{10}(\text{FO}_4)_4.4(\text{AsO}_4)_{1.6}(\text{OH})_2$	1309.77	3.582	365.60	1.667	9.14	6.74
4.	46.99	7.03	17.15	$\text{Cu}_{10}(\text{FO}_4)_3.1(\text{AsO}_4)_{2.9}(\text{OH})_2$	1366.87	3.612	378.40	1.621	9.30	6.85
5.	45.33	5.69	19.77	$\text{Cu}_{10}(\text{FO}_4)_2.3(\text{AsO}_4)_{3.7}(\text{OH})_2$	1402.01	3.642	384.90	1.596	9.42	6.92
6.	43.69	2.34	25.24	$\text{Cu}_{10}(\text{FO}_4)_{1.1}(\text{AsO}_4)_{4.9}(\text{OH})_2$	1454.71	3.680	395.30	1.667	9.56	7.02
7.	42.28	—	29.91	$\text{Cu}_{10}(\text{AsO}_4)_6(\text{OH})_2$	1503.02	3.702	406.00	1.666	9.64	7.12

Results and Discussion

Results of chemical analyses and molar volumes of samples are given in Table 1. Molecular formulae for each of the samples was assigned on the basis of results of chemical analysis. Observed value of molar g. atomic ratio (theoretical 1.67) of Cu/P and Cu/As for end members and

$\frac{\text{Cu}}{\text{P+As}}$ for others and closeness of the values of

molar volumes of end members and those for intermediate samples which lie within the range of end members is to indicate the formation of homogeneous solid solutions⁶.

Homogeneity and crystallinity of the samples were further confirmed by the values of lattice parameters of the samples. It is well established that all the members of apatite family exhibit hexagonal crystals belonging to hexagonal bipyramidal class 6/m (space group $C_{6h}^{3/m}$). The lattice parameters showed unit cell dialation consequent upon the introduction of bigger ion $(\text{AsO}_4)^{3-}$ in place of $(\text{PO}_4)^{3-}$ ion in the apatite lattice.

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Spectrophotometric Determination of Micro Amounts of Gold(III) with Fluphenazine Hydrochloride and Promazine Hydrochloride

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PROMAZINE hydrochloride, PMH, 10-[3-(dimethylamino)propyl]-phenothiazine hydrochloride was proposed for the spectrophotometric determination of palladium(II)¹. A survey of chemical literature has shown that no attempt has been made to use PMH and fluphenazine hydrochloride, FPH, 4-[3-(2-trifluoromethyl)-phenothiazine-10-yl]-propyl-1-piperazine-ethanol-hydrochloride as spectrophotometric reagents for gold(III). The present paper describes FPH and PMH as new sensitive spectrophotometric reagents for the determination of Au(III).

Experimental

Chemicals and reagents: A stock solution of 400 ppm of gold(III) was prepared by dissolving gold(III) chloride (Baird and Tatlock, London) in dilute AnalaR hydrochloric acid and diluted to 1 litre to give 1M with respect to hydrochloric acid. The solution was standardised gravimetrically by the hydroquinone method². Aqueous 0.2% solutions of FPH and PMH were prepared in doubly distilled water and stored in a refrigerator. A Beckman Model DB spectrophotometer with stoppered 1 cm silica cells was used for the absorbance measurements.

Procedure for the Determination of Au :

(i) *with FPH:* Transfer an aliquot of the stock solution containing 5-425 μg of Au(III) to a 25 ml